

A Study on Impact of Information Technology in Banking Sector -Special Reference with Ramanathapuram

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Abstract

The impact of information technology on work life has been one of the most talked about issues over the recent years. Information technology provides economies of scale in service delivery, covering new customers and developing innovative services. It adopts internet, mobile, and communication systems to deliver speedy service. The data for the study collected through well-constructed and open-ended questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed and drawn meaningful inferences with the help of various tools such as simple percentage analysis, and weighted average score analysis. The study provides various suggestions for banks to improve the effective utilization of technology.

Introduction

The Indian banking sector is also trying to wake up from sleep and become proactive till 1990; the Indian banks have been working in a very comfortable and protected environment. However, since then they have been pushed into intense competition due to changed economic policies. The technology is lifting the competition in the banking sector. Traditionally, banks have been using technology to improve their products and efficiency. Today, technology is not only changing the environment but also the relationship with customers. Technology has not broken many barriers but has also brought about superior products and channels. This has brought customer relationship into greater focus. It is also viewed as an instrument of cost reduction and effective communication with people and institutions associated with the banking business. The RBI has assigned priority to the up gradation of technological infrastructure in the financial system. Technology has opened new product and services, new market and efficient delivery channels the banking industry. IT also provides the framework the banking industry to meet challenges in the present competitive environment. IT enables to cut the cost of global fund transfer.

The Objective of the Study

1. Recent IT Trends of Indian banks.
2. The demographic profile of bank customers.
3. The Factors Influencing Service Accessibility.

Recent IT Trends of Indian Banks⁵

The banking industry is going through a period of rapid change to meet competition, challenges of technology and the demand of end user. Clearly, technology is a key differentiator in the performance of banks. Banks need to look at innovation not just for product but for process also. Today, technology is not only changing the environment but also the relationship with customers. This has brought customer relationship into greater focus. It is an instrument of cost reduction and effective communication with people and institutions associated with the banking business. Some of the recent IT devices described as below:

Electronic Payment and Settlement System

The most common media of receipts and payment through banks are negotiable instruments like cheques. These instruments could be used in place of cash. The inter bank cheques could be realized through clearing house systems. Initially, there was a manual system of clearing, but the growing volume of banking transaction emerged into the necessity of automating the clearing process. To strengthen the institutional framework the electronic & clearing system, RBI constituted a board for regulation and supervision of payment and settlement system (BPSS) in 2005.

Use of MICR Technology

Among the most important improvement in paper-based clearing system was the introduction of MICR (Magnetic Ink Character Recognition) in the mid-1980s. MICR overcomes the limitation of clearing the cheques within banking hours and thus enables the customer to get the credit quickly.

Cheque Transaction System

The CTS was launched on pilot basis in New Delhi in 2008 with the participation of 10 Banks. Truncation means stopping the flow of the physical cheques issued by a drawer to the drawee branch.

Electronic Clearing Services

The Electronic Clearing Services introduced by Reserve bank of India in 1995 which is similar to automated clearing houses that are operational in other countries like US. The ECS was the first version of “Electronic Payments” in India. It is a mode of electronic funds transfer from one bank account to another bank account using the mechanism of clearing house.

Electronic Clearing Services - Credit

Electronic Clearing Services credit clearing operates on the principle of „single debit multiple credits and is used for transactions like payment of salary, dividend, pension, interest etc

Electronic Clearing Services -Debit

Electronic Clearing Services debit clearing service operates on the principle of „single credit multiple debits and is used by utility service providers the collection of electricity bills, telephone bills, and other charges and also by banks for collections of principal and interest repayments.

Electronic Fund Transfer

The EFT System was implemented in 1995 covering 15 centers where the Reserve Bank managed the clearing houses. Special EFT (SEFT) scheme, a variant of the EFT system, was introduced with effect from April 1, 2003, in order to increase the coverage of the scheme and to provide for quicker funds transfers.

Real Time Gross Settlement

RTGS was launched by RBI in 2004 which enabled a real-time settlement on a gross basis. RTGS system is a funds transfer mechanism the transfer of money takes place from one bank to another on a “real-time” and on “gross basis”. This is the fastest possible money transfer system through the banking channel.

Core Banking Solutions

Computerization of bank branches had started with installation of simple computers to automate the functioning of branches, especially at high traffic branches. Core Banking Solutions (CBS) is the networking of the branches of a bank, so as to enable the customers to operate their accounts from any bank branch, regardless of which branch he opened the account.

Development of Distribution Channels

The major and upcoming channels of distribution in the banking industry, besides branches are ATMs, internet banking, mobile and telephone banking and card based delivery systems.

Automated Teller Machine (ATM)

ATMs were introduced to the Indian banking industry in the early 1990s initiated by foreign banks. It is perhaps most revolutionary aspect of virtual banking. The facility to use ATM is provided through plastic cards with magnetic strip containing information about the customer as well as the bank. In today’s world ATMs are the most useful tool to ensure the concept of “Any Time Banking” and “Anywhere Banking”.

Tele Banking

Tele banking is another innovation, which provided the facility of 24-hour banking to the customer. Telebanking is based on the voice processing facility available on bank computers. The caller usually a customer calls the bank anytime and can enquire balance in his account or other transaction history. Tele banking is becoming popular since queries at ATMs are now becoming too long.

Internet Banking

Internet banking enables a customer to do banking transactions through the bank’s website on the Internet. It is a system of accessing accounts, general information on bank products, and services through a computer while sitting in its office or home. This is also called virtual banking.

Mobile Banking

Mobile banking facility is an extension of internet banking. Mobile banking services are provided to the customers having the credit card accounts the bank. In mobile banking, the services are provided by the association of banks and cellular service providers through SMS or WAP enabled mobile instruments.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

It refers to the methodologies and tools that help businesses manage customer relationships in an organized way-finding, getting and retaining customer. CRM processes that help to provide employees with the information they need to know their customers' wants and needs and build relationships between the company and its customers.

Analysis of Demographic Profile

The demographic profile of bank customers is analyzed presented in Table-1. Simple percentage analysis has been adopted to analyze demographic profiles of respondents.

Table 1 Gender Wise Classification of Respondents

S.No.	Gender	Respondents	Percentage
1.	Male	121	80.66
2.	Female	29	19.44
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

It is the above from table1 that the gender level shows that about 80.66 percent are male respondents while the rest 19.44 percent is female respondents.

Table 2 Age wise classification of Respondents

S.No.	Age	Respondents	Percentage
1	20- 25	25	16.67
2	26-35	31	20.67
3	36-45	44	29.33
4	46-55	29	19.33
5	Above 55	21	14
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 gives the age wise classification of the sample respondents the above table shows that among the 150 respondents selected for the study 37.24 percentage of the respondents belong to an aged group of 25-35 and 48.66 percentages of the respondents belong to an age group of 36-55, remaining 14 percentages belong to an age group of above 55.

Table 3 Education Qualifications

S.No.	Age	Respondents	Percentage
1	Illiterate	15	10.00
2	Up to HSC	47	31.33
3	Dip/Degree	56	37.33
4	P.G/Professional	32	21.34
	Total	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The Table 3 further states that 21.34 percent of the respondents are Post Graduate/Professional, 37.33 percent of the respondents are Diploma/ Graduate, 31.33 percent of the respondents are Higher Secondary, and 10.00 percent of the respondents are Illiterate.

Table 4 Occupation wise Classification

Sl.No.	Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Government employee	38	25.33
2	Private employee	36	24.00
3	Professional	28	18.67
4	Business	25	16.67
5	Others	23	15.33
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 reveals that out of 150 respondents, 25.33 percentage of respondents belong to government employees, 24 percentage of respondents belong to private employee, the professional and business people were 18.67 percentage of respondents and 16.67 percentage of respondents respectively and the remaining comes under others category.

Table 5 Source of Income

S.No.	Income	Respondents	Percentage
1.	10000-20000	19	12.67
2.	20000-30000	39	26.00
3	30000-40000	47	31.33
4	40000-50000	27	18.00
5	50000-60000	18	12.00
	Total	150	100

Table 5 that 12.67 percent of the respondents whose monthly income varies in between Rs10, 000 to 20,000, 26 percent of the respondents whose monthly income varies in between Rs20, 000 to 30, 000,. 31.33percent of the respondents whose monthly income varies in between above Rs30, 000 to 40,000 and the remaining 30 percent of the respondents whose monthly income vary in between Rs 40, 000 to 60, 000.

Table 6 Type of Services

S.No.	Type of Services	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Internet Banking	20	13.33
2	Mobile Banking	23	15.33
3	Ticket booking	27	18.00
4	Bill Payment	21	14.00
5	Prepaid Mobile Recharge	12	08.00
6	Funds Transfer (e Cheques)	16	10.67
7	Online Payment of Excise & Service Tax,	13	08.67
8	Smart Money Order	07	04.67
9	Card to Card Funds Transfer	11	07.33
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

The table 6 Show that the type of service access the customer 18 percent of the respondents are ticket booking service,15.33 percent of the respondents are mobile banking, 14 percent of the respondents are use bill payment, 13.33 percent of the respondents are internet banking, and Reaming 39.34 percent of the respondents are use Prepaid Mobile Recharge, Funds Transfer (e Cheques), Online Payment of Excise & Service Tax, Smart Money Order, Card to Card Funds Transfer.

Table 7 Frequency of Use

S.No.	Frequency of use	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Daily	38	25.33
2	Weekly	45	30.00
3	Weekly Twice	27	18.00
4	Monthly	21	14.00
5	Monthly Twice	19	12.67
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

The table 7 that the frequent customer use for 30 percent of the respondents are weakly,25.33 percent of the respondents are Daily,18 percent of the respondents are respondents are weekly twice and 26.67 percent of the respondents are monthly, and monthly twice.

Table 8 Factors Influencing Service Accessibility

SI.No.	Particulars	SA	A	M		DA	SDA	Total Score	AVG Score	Rank
I	Banking Services									
	Mobile banking	38	44	30		20	18	514	3.42	VI
	Core banking	40	30	44		22	14	510	3.40	VII
	Debit and credit cards	48	36	26		24	16	526	3.50	IV
	ATM facility	50	42	30		18	10	554	3.69	I
	Electronic Fund Transfer	46	44	26		20	14	538	3.58	III
	ECS facility	42	46	24		18	20	522	3.48	V
II	Add-on Services & Delivery									
	24x7 Service access	50	36	28		20	16	534	3.56	V
	Service quality improvement	58	42	34		10	6	586	3.90	I
	Balance/Statement inquiry	42	48	28		18	14	536	3.57	IV
	Cheque book facility	44	54	26		14	12	554	3.69	III
	Demat services	42	40	26		22	20	512	3.41	VI
	Loan applications	47	56	21		15	11	563	3.75	II
III	Front Office Services									
	Speedy service	54	42	30		14	10	566	3.77	I
	Short waiting time	44	38	34		18	16	520	3.46	IV
	Guidance on service access	34	46	30		26	14	510	3.40	V
	Cash withdrawal	48	36	32		22	12	536	3.57	II
	Retail banking	36	52	34		16	12	534	3.56	III

IV	Safety of Services									
	Convenient ATM Location	46	40	28		20	16	530	3.53	V
	Advanced Technology	54	40	38		12	6	574	3.82	I
	Transparency	48	42	24		22	14	538	3.58	IV
	Balance enquiry and maintenance	44	48	32		14	12	548	3.65	II
	Better control on transactions	48	42	30		16	14	544	3.62	III
V	Technology- Enabled Services									
	Friendly technology to adapt	46	40	28		20	16	530	3.53	IV
	Less cost	54	40	38		12	6	574	3.82	II
	Adequate voice prompts	48	42	24		22	14	538	3.58	III
	Access to necessity	58	61	19		7	5	610	4.06	I
VI	Reliability of Service									
	Error- free service	41	62	21		16	10	387	2.58	II
	Familiar with service	54	59	23		8	6	59	3.98	I

Source: Primary Data

SA – Strongly Agree, A - Agree, M – Moderately Agree, DA – Disagree, SDA – Strongly Disagree

Table 7 **Factors Influencing Service Accessibility.** These factors were generated by the literature and were classified into Six broader categories of

1. Banking Services,
2. Add-on Services & Delivery,
3. Front Office Services,
4. Safety of Services,
5. Technology- Enabled Services and
6. Reliability of Service

Table 7 **Factors Influencing Service Accessibility**, the weighted ranking method applied. **In first Statement is Banking Services.** It inferred that the most number of the respondents have given the first ranked for ATM Facilities; the respondents had given the Second rank for internet banking. The third rank was Electronic Fund Transfer, and followed by Debit, and credit cards, and ECS facility. **In Second Statement is Add-on Services & Delivery** It is clear that the most number of the respondents have given the first ranked for Service quality improvement, the respondents had given the Second rank for Poor Loan applications, and the third rank was Cheque book facility. **In Third Statement is Front Office Services.** It is understood that the most number of the respondents had given the first ranked for Speedy service; the respondents had given the Second rank for Find out the Cash withdrawal. The third rank was Improper Market Condition and followed by Retail banking. **The fourth Statement is Safety of Services** It is shown that the most number of the respondents had given first ranked for Advanced Technology, the respondents had given the Second rank for Balance enquiry and maintenance, and the third rank was Better control on transactions. **The fifth Statement is Technology- Enabled Services.** It is above that the most number of the respondents had given the first ranked for Access on necessity; the respondents had given the Second rank for less cost. The third rank was adequate voice prompts and followed by Friendly technology to adapt. **The sixth Statement is Reliability of Service.** It inferred that the most number of the respondents had given the first ranked for Familiar on service and the respondents had given the Second rank for Error free service.

Conclusion

Information Technology offers enormous potential and various opportunities to the Indian banking sector. It provides cost-effective, rapid and systematic provision of services to the customer. The study emphasizes on the percentage of awareness on maximum utilization of technology. Banks should take effective measures in creating awareness towards the effective usage of technology.

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